

INTEGRATING ETHICS BOWL IN ETHICS COURSES: EXPERIENCES OF THE MECHANICAL ENGINEERING PROGRAMS OF MAPUA INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY AND DE LA SALLE UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: The Mechanical Engineering programs of Mapua Institute of Technology and De La Salle University have been continually striving to strengthen the ability of students to properly handle and resolve future ethical dilemmas that they may experience over the course of their engineering career. An ideal venue for imbuing future mechanical engineers with a strong sense of moral autonomy is the course Mechanical Engineering Ethics. One of the methods utilized by these engineering schools is the integration of ethics bowl within the course. Ethics bowl is an activity that requires students to resolve moral dilemmas in a competitive environment utilizing various principles learned in class. The activity challenges students to resolve moral dilemmas within the classroom environment, allowing the instructor to immediately give feedback on the responses of students to cases on ethics.

Keywords: engineering ethics, ethics bowl

1. Introduction

The Intercollegiate Ethics Bowl (IEB) was developed in 1993 by Dr. Ladenson. The competition, which at the start was only held at the Illinois Institute of Technology for two years, grew into what is now a nationwide event that in the United States. Due to the increase in the number of Educational Institutions that wish to join the competition, regional competitions were held where only the top teams were eligible to participate in the national competition.

With the permission of Dr. Ladenson, the IEB was introduced in the Philippines in 2003 by one of the authors, Dr. Belino, as an interdepartmental competition within the College of Engineering of the De La Salle University- Manila. Since then, the IEB has become an inter-university competition and is now attended by representatives from at least 12 schools from the South Manila Inter-Institutional Consortium [1].

The event has attracted increased participation partly due to the many educational benefits it may offer and provide. Since only a limited pool of students may participate in the official Ethics Bowl events, the classroom could be a venue for holding such an event to allow more students to participate in the competition, maximizing the educational benefits of the IEB.

2. Ethics Bowl Description and Benefits

The Ethics Bowl is an event that provides the opportunity for participants to be involved in both a rich educational experience and an exciting team-based competition [2]. Shown below is a list of the benefits that students may derive from the activity, as was further noted by Dr. Ladenson:

- Develops both intellectual and well-organized manner of thinking in tackling ethical issues.
- Provides valuable background information regarding ethical issues that may be relevant to their individual interests, concerns and career aspirations.
- Strengthens the understanding of ethics over a wide array of important issues.

The Ethics Bowl assigned as a learning activity in class has been implemented with varying methodologies by several Schools. Many of such Schools who have done so have reported the many benefits experienced by students and instructors. In a classroom setting, based on the experience of Cruz et al., the Ethics Bowl may provide benefits to students in the following areas: communication skills, organization of thoughts, argument formulation, clarity in oral presentation of opinion, teamwork and moral autonomy and ethical thinking [3].

The benefits provided by the implementation of the Ethics Bowl in class also coincide with the expectations from Outcomes-Based Education (OBE). In OBE, students are expected to know and/or perform various relevant skills, knowledge and behaviour by the time of graduation. This is also in relation to the Commission on Higher Education's identified Program Outcomes for Colleges and Universities that offer a bachelor degree program in Mechanical Engineering, which states that students should develop the ability to understand their ethical responsibility. The Ethics Bowl application to the course in engineering ethics can lead towards the Schools' attainment of relevant program outcomes.

3. Classroom Environment Implementation

This section highlights the methodologies used for the conduct of the mini-ethics bowl in the ethics courses offered by the mechanical engineering program of both De La Salle University-Manila and Mapua Institute of Technology.

3.1 Implementation by the Department of Mechanical Engineering, De La Salle University- Manila

One of the requirements of the course ME Laws, Ethics, Codes and Standards at DLSU is the conduct of a mini – ethics bowl in class. The students are divided into several groups with a maximum of four members in a group. Each group is provided with a compilation of at least 20 case studies for them to read and analyse. The groups have to identify the ethical issues involved in each of the cases and be able to defend in class how they are going to resolve such issues. The cases included several ethical concerns such as conflict of interest, bribery and extortion, environmental ethics, research and mentoring, authorship, intellectual property, public safety and professional responsibility.

On the day of the event, a representative from each group draws lots to determine the sequence of presentation. The first group picks up a case from a bowl containing 20 cases, after which the case selected is read aloud. The group then is given five minutes to confer with each other and another ten minutes to present their analysis of the case. After the presentation, the other students and the judges will ask questions with regard to the analysis presented by the group. The same procedures are repeated for other groups.

The criteria used for judging are as follows:

- a. Clarity and Intelligibility (25%) – It tells us whether the students were able to state and defend their position in a way that it is logically consistent and that the judges were able to understand the team's line of reasoning clearly.
- b. Depth and Substance (25%) – It tells us whether the team had identified and discussed the factors that are considered by the judges as ethically relevant in relation to the case.
- c. Ethical Relevance (25%) – It tells us whether the team had stayed on track by avoiding preoccupation with issues that are considered ethically irrelevant by the judges.
- d. Deliberative Thoughtfulness (25%) - It tells us whether the team's presentation of its position with regard to the case indicates both awareness and thoughtful consideration of different viewpoints, including those of individuals who may disagree with their analysis.

The groups that get the highest scores will be announced winners in the mini – ethics bowl competition.

3.2 Implementation by the School of Mechanical Engineering, Mapua Institute of Technology

As part of the Continuous Quality Improvement Efforts of School of Mechanical Engineering of Mapua Institute of Technology, constant fine tuning have been done to continuously improve its various course offerings, including its course on engineering ethics. The Ethics Bowl was implemented in the past as part of the requirements for the course, and is planned to be reinstalled in the succeeding academic quarters.

At some point during the term after the lectures on engineering ethics have been given, special activities are provided to students. One of such activities is the intra-class Ethics Bowl. A few days before the activity, important information (e.g. the rationale, rules and the grading scheme) are provided. Students are assigned to random groups to reflect real life situations when individuals at times do not have the liberty to choose the people they work with. The class is usually divided into three to four groups, each composed of at least five members. The grading system utilized is very similar to that shown in the previous section, and also based on the tools used in the annual Inter-School Ethics Bowl in the Philippines.

For the conduct of the activity, the groups would randomly pick a number which represents the case number to be assigned to them. The cases would be flashed in front of the class and will be assigned to the different groups. All groups would then be given fifteen minutes to deliberate and resolve the moral dilemma presented, utilizing various principles covered in the course. A member is assigned as a secretary of the group and is in-charge of noting key points in the group's deliberation and position. After the given time has expired, the first group will be given five minutes to present their view on the case. Ample time is given for non-presenting

groups to critic and question the presenting group's response, while the presenting group is given an opportunity to provide rebuttals to questions posed by other groups and the judges. The next group would then be given the chance to give their response after the first group has completed the round. The process would then be repeated until all groups have given their responses and rebuttals.

4. Experience in Implementation

In the conduct of the mini-ethics bowl in the classroom, several observations have been noted by the faculty members handling the course. It was noted that the students were able to strengthen their values of teamwork and cooperation, since the activity demands that each student contribute and participate to ensure a much effective response and resolution of the cases provided. The students have also been exposed to several case studies involving one or more ethical issues, on top of what is provided to them during examinations and lectures. This exposure to ethical problem solving requires the process of analysis, and thus developed their intellectual capabilities, deepened their ethical understanding and strengthened their commitment to ethical concerns.

During the presentation, students were able to develop their confidence and reasoning abilities as they defended their position orally. It also made the students realize that in some way, their position may not always be the most ethical way of resolving the issues. The Ethics Bowl was a good learning experience, considering that everyone participated and interacted with each other during the entire activity.

Students mostly were both excited and nervous during the competition since they felt the pressure of the contest, but were also feeling the "rush" brought about by the competitive nature of the activity. Students felt less shy while presenting their arguments orally, since most of the participants have known each other due to being together for several years in their undergraduate education. It was also observed that students who usually are reluctant to participate and express themselves in class often become active and interactive during the activity.

There are, however, challenges in implementing the activity in a classroom environment. One consideration is the additional demand on instructors in terms of providing new cases to constantly expand the database, so as to limit recycling of questions during the succeeding academic terms. Time restriction brought about by the limited time to cover the prescribed topics within the course proves to be a consideration as well. The time allotment for every meeting of the class, which ranges from one to one and a half hours, may also be a factor that could negatively impact the activity. In such cases, modified schedules may be done to augment class schedule limitations.

5. Recommendations

The authors strongly recommend the following to instructors who wish to implement the Ethics Bowl as a learning activity in their respective courses:

- Be familiarized with the various rules and judging criteria available while drafting those that will be used in class so that one may be aware of the best practices that are adaptable to their own respective conditions.

- Choose the best schedule and venue to get the most out of the benefits of the mini-Ethics Bowl.
- Strategize the best student-group ratio that would best satisfy the objectives of the course. Too many students in a group tend to diminish participation of some individuals, while too many groups could consume too much time and would leave many bored while waiting for their turn to participate.
- Involve other stakeholders (e.g. faculty members, industry practitioners) as judges to not only provide fresh input relevant to their own fields of specialization, but also to further professional growth by their participation in discussions on ethics.
- Apply assessment methodologies for OBE to clearly and accurately measure student learning, which can be used in evaluation of the program outcomes.

References

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